

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PEDAGOGY OF SINGING TECHNIQUES.

Akhmedov Mukhtarali Askarovich

Teacher of Namangan state university

Ermatova Madinabonu Biloliddin kizi

Student of Namangan state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7783728>

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the methods of music teachers in the lessons of music culture, the skills of students and the basic knowledge of vocal singing.

Keywords: method, music, culture, teacher, education, student, person, interest, pedagogy.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о методах работы учителей музыки на уроках музыкальной культуры, о навыках учащихся и базовых знаниях вокального пения.

Ключевые слова: метод, музыка, культура, учитель, воспитание, ученик, личность, интерес, педагогика.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada musiqa madaniyati darslarida musiqa o'qituvchilarining dars o'tishlaridagi metodlari, talaba yoshlar vokal xonandaligi bo'yicha boshlang'ich bilimlarni haqidagi ko'nikmalar haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: metod, musiqa, madaniyat, o'qituvchi, tarbiya, talaba, inson, qiziqish, pedagogika.

When it comes to singing technique, we always hear movements filled with emotional embellishments in vocal singing performances. Sounds and images guide the performer on the method of performance, the technical side helps to apply them to the performance, so the singing technique determines how the musical performance will be. The feeling of being able to feel the music should be developed simultaneously with the technique of singing. The technique should be built on the basis of musical material, which should be understandable to students.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts [1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 " On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan

No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3]. Ensuring the development and prospects of the Republic of Uzbekistan depends on the changes taking place in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres, and in order to actively participate in such changes, high-level general and special knowledge, intellectual capacity, broad outlook and skillful use of information communications are required. Based on these requirements, the training of pedagogic personnel is one of the most important tasks of today.

The task of the teacher is to develop the student’s taste for music and artistic skills, to teach them to understand the musical language, and to awaken their creative imagination. Students studying in educational institutions can have basic knowledge of youth vocal singing. This is not enough in training a true vocal singer. They were not in a musical environment even in childhood, so their musical sense is not developed. Musical sense can be developed in all young people and is necessary and important for their creativity. Today, all the bases are sufficient for the development of talent under certain conditions.[4]

The human nervous system is constantly growing and changing according to the demands of the environment. To be able to feel music, that is, to understand the musical language, to perceive its meaning - if one approaches this task correctly, it is possible for all people to one degree or another. A sense of pitch, a sense of rhythm, a sense of chords, harmonic hearing and a sense of other musical elements can be developed. During a live performance, one can learn to understand existence and its meaning through musical language. Teaching the student to discover the meaning of music is one of the main tasks of the teacher, and he must carry out this process at the same time as mastering the musical technique.

Music should be able to be a language that speaks about human feelings, emotions and images. In this place, it is necessary to choose the repertoire correctly. Before choosing the repertoire, it is advisable to choose easy-to-understand works, and later, gradually more complex ones. It should also be noted that there are Uzbek and Caucasian versions of the epics in the series “Gorogly”. [5]

It is necessary to solve two tasks in training a singer. These are the ability to hear the executive apparatus and see its possibilities. That is, a professional singer should feel the “sound” of his voice. The next task is to listen to this sound and play a piece of music on it. These processes are closely related to each other.

This is the important and difficult aspect of the singer's musical education, which is fundamentally different from the education of musical performers. Therefore, in this step, the teacher creates the voice of the singer, that is, performs the task of “training the voice”.

At the beginning of education, exercises are given for the elementary knowledge of the correct formation of the voice, and even these meaningless (textless) exercises are given importance to perform with musicality. Every mistake and even the simplest knowledge should be related to elementary executive tasks. Musical exercises can be sung as a simple sequence of notes or, conversely, as a developed musical thought.[6]

Vocal performers should put the musical image in the first place when performing a piece and during the performance of the piece. Thus, the vocal technique of the singer should be connected with the musical imagination from the first exercises to the perfect performance.

The following three stages are among the most important in mastering musical knowledge. The first of these is to choose the right way to work on the voice apparatus, the second is to determine the process of strengthening this way, and the third is to develop and maintain it. Teachers and students are required to always remember these three stages. Mastering the multifaceted aspects of singing knowledge helps to approach the work creatively and achieve freedom of performance.

References:

1. Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. Activity of Mutal Burkhanov House Museum. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY VOLUME: 03 ISSUE: 11 | NOV 2022 (ISSN: 2660-6836). 76-81 pp. <https://scienceweb.uz/publication/4566>
2. Topildiev Odiljon Rakhimjonovich, Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. REFORM IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. Web of scientist: International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 5, May., 2022.196-198 pp.
3. Mirhakimova, F. K. (2021). The state museum of history and culture of Namangan region past and today. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(8), 84-89.
4. Solomonova T. History of Uzbek music. T. 1981.- P.14.
5. FERUZA, M. Chust Culture Heart-Bibiona. JournalNX, 6(05), 4-6. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=dmNy-zEAAA&AJ&citation_for_view=dmNy-zEAAA&AJ:7PzIFSSx8tAC
6. Bekmatov S. Household art. Instructional manual.-T: 2007. – P. 45.